

SANDVIK SURFACE TECHNOLOGY: A SOLUTION FOR MASS PRODUCTION OF FUEL CELLS

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Sandvik Surface Technology offers a portfolio of cost effective pre-coated steel strips for electronics applications, interconnects for Solid Oxide Cells (SOC) and bipolar plates for Polymer Electrolyte Fuel Cells (PEM). Coils of any steel grade according to customer specifications with a width smaller than 800 mm and a thickness between 0.07 and 0.8 mm are introduced in the coating line (Figure 1). Prior coming to the coating line the coils are cleaned by a wet chemical de-greasing process, followed by surface inspection. This process is followed by an in-line plasma cleaning/etching. In the next process the metal layers are deposited on the coil by Sandvik's continuous PVD coating process. The coating thickness and uniformity is monitored with X-ray inspection systems. Before shipping, the coils are going through testing, slitting and packaging processes according to customer specifications.

Sandvik Sanergy™ HT 441 have been shown excellent properties as SOC interconnect. The material is an ASTM 441 steel grade with a double coating of Ce and Co. The material has shown to form a protective spinel layer with a $(\text{Co},\text{Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ composition by diffusion of Mn from the steel over time. This spinel phase is well known to reduce Cr vaporization which leads to loss of stack performance by electrode poisoning. The addition of Ce reduces the growth rate of the highly electric resistant Cr_2O_3 layer. In addition, the pre-coated coil developed by Sandvik has excellent self-healing properties. Because of all these properties, Sandvik Sanergy™ HT 441 shows excellent surface conductivity. After more than 35000 h of exposure the material shows ASR values below $50 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ and a degradation rate of less than $1 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per 1000 h. These are values within the specifications required for the SOC stack manufacturers.

Figure 1. Schematics of the roll to roll coating line developed in Sandviken (Sweden) and the cost-effective advantage of our pre-coated solution versus the conventional batch method.

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